

DETERMINANTS OF STRESS AND MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES AMONG ACADEMIC STAFF AT NNAMDI AZIKIWE UNIVERSITY

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Abstract: This study examined the determinants of stress among tertiary Institutions academic staff, a study of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The main objective of the study is to evaluate the root cause of stress on the academic staff of tertiary institutions and the effect of stress on the academic staff of tertiary institutions. The research used primary source of data applied via questionnaire and interview method to a sample of 303 respondents from the selected tertiary (Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka). The findings revealed a significant relationship between stress and the academic staff performance and concluded that a significant relationship does exist. The studies recommend among others that academic staff should not be overloaded with course work and other administrative responsibilities as well the establishment of a thorough communication system in the tertiary institution.

Keywords: Stress; Tertiary Institutions; Academic Staff; Nnamdi Azikiwe University.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Agreeably, management's focus on the use of organizational resources is to attain goals. However, management is usually constrained by the unavoidability and inadequacy of the resources - man, machine, money and materials (4ms) in its pursuit of the attainment of corporate objectives. Due to limited supply of corporate resources, it makes sense that management must seek to optimally blend or combine its limited available resources in the manners that will lead to the achievement of group and organizational objectives.

Among all the resources of an organization, man or human resources stands out because it takes human dexterity or ingenuity to combine all corporate resources in an optimal manner. Little wonder the human resources are called a very important asset in every organization (Cole, 2005). The success of any organization is generally said to be a function of good employees. This management belief has remained since the past world war era (Cole, 2005). Employees, if well managed can impact positively on the profit of an organization because every employee's performance relates strongly to the attainment of corporate goal. Sometimes, however, certain factors tend to influence employee performance. One of such factors is stress according to Bryant (2001) is critical because of its psychological undertone and implications. With increasing demands of home and work life, employees are under enormous stress Cole (2005) define stress as the adverse psychological and physical reactions that occurs in individual as a result of their being unable to cope with the demands being made of them. It is the "wear and tear" that our bodies experience as we adjust to our continually changing environment. This has physical and emotional effects on employees/individual and can create positively or negatively feelings (Braxton and Gold, 1999). Stress can therefore, influence employee positively or negatively. As a positive influence it can result in a new awareness and an exciting new perspectives, while as a negative influence, it can result to feelings of distrust, rejection, anger and depression, which in turn can lead to health problems such as headache, stomach upset, rashes, insomnia, ulcers, high blood pressure, heart diseases and stroke (Colbert, 2005). With the death of loved one, the birth of a child, a job promotion or a new relationship, people experience stress as they readjust themselves to life. In adjusting to different circumstances, stress helps to hinder employees depending on how they react to it (Colbert, 2005).

As a result of the negative impact of stress usually have on employee performance and indeed, on profitability, employers are increasingly paying greater attention to the causes of stress on the employees, especially on their key management personnel. Adequate response to stress narrows one's susceptibility to become much infected. This is because stress can disable one physically and emotionally. However, the goal of stress management is to bring one's nervous system back into balance, giving the individual or employee, a sense of calmness and control in his/her work and life.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

There is stress epidemic in the private and public sectors due to global economic meltdown that has brought with it, serious pressures on cooperate bodies (and indeed their workforce) as a result of the composition of their domestic and social life. Undoubtedly stress affects employee performance, which by extension affects profit potentials of an organization. In Nigeria, stress is gradually becoming a serious issue, especially in the public sector. In the light of the on-going reform programmes of the government, most staff work long hours with consideration pressure to meet deadlines and targets. The Nnamdi Azikiwe University staffs are not left out. Lecture schedules are too tight, overcrowded and overloaded. There are numerous programmes - regular, CEP, sandwich, pre-science and post graduate, etc all begging for attention by university management and students. The economic meltdown compelled the staff to work continuously, and around the clock in order to meet the academic or sessional deadlines, hence compounding stress situations. Apparently, the excessive workload of the teaching staff has contributed to the stressful experiences in most universities in Nigeria. The problem of this study of this study therefore, rest on finding out the factors that actually causes stress among Nnamdi Azikiwe University teaching staff, with a view to highlighting appropriate measures to deal with them.

The objective of this study is to identify the root causes of stress among the teaching staff of academic institutions, study of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

Stress: Meaning and Overview

The term 'stress' is now part of the regular vocabulary of managers and employees. While some stresses are normal or to life, if stress persists or is prolonged, individuals experience physical and psychological discomfort. The experience of work can lead to a variety of symptoms of stress that harm employees' health and job performance. Much research in the area of job stress has focused on individuals in the higher echelons of the organizational hierarchy (Bratton and Gold, 1999). However, stress can affect employees at lower levels as well. It has been shown through research that stress can lead to physical and psychological disabilities (Bratton and Gold, 1999). in addition to physical and psychological disabilities, job stress costs individuals and business considerable sum of money. Increasingly, employers are beginning to pay greater attention than in the past to the effects of stress on their staff, especially on their key management personnel. What is stress? According to Cole (2000) "it can best be described in lay terms as the adverse psychological and physical reaction that occur in individuals as results of their being unable to cope with the demands being made on them". Colbert (2005) defines stress as the "pressure of life and how one perceives, believes, reacts, and copes with these pressures". Another definition from Webster's is "a physical, chemical, or emotional factor in disease causation". Colbert (2005) argued that the body's stress response involves more than fourteen hundred known physical and chemical reactions involving more than thirty different hormones and neurotransmitters. Excessive release of "stress hormones", he further argued, damages cells, tissue, and organs.

TYPICAL SYMPTOMS OF STRESS

Bratton and Gold (1999) outlined the following as symptoms that indicate the existence of stress in individuals:

- | | |
|----------------------|--------------------|
| Tension anxiety | Sleep problems |
| Anger and aggression | Digestive problems |

High blood pressure

Chronic worry

Inability to relax

Irritability and boredom

Excessive alcohol use

Excessive tobacco use

Uncooperative attitudes

Forgetfulness

Increased accident

Increased absenteeism

Reduces job satisfaction

Symptoms of stress, according to Cole (2000), are typically analyzed under three headings: **physiological, psychological and behavioural.**

Physiological Symptoms: In addition to short-term reactions such increased heartbeat, tensed muscles and extra adrenalin secretion which are human beings' instinctive reaction to danger, the chronic (ie longer term) effects of stress are associated with such unhealthy conditions as coronary heart disease, High blood pressure, indigestion, gastric ulcers, back pain and even cancer. Stress is also likely to be manifested in less serious infections, allergies and physical disorders.

Psychological Symptoms: In chronic situations the psychological symptoms of stress tend to manifest in anxiety states (Phobias. Obsessions etc) and depression. In less serious conditions, stress emerges in the form of tension, irritability, boredom and job dissatisfaction.

Behavioural Symptoms: Ultimately the psychological and psychological symptoms lead to generalized changes in behaviour such as loss of appetite, increase cigarette smoking and alcohol consumption, and sleeplessness. In the workplace behaviour may take the form increase absences (flight), aggression towards colleague's tasks. In utterly intolerable conditions individual may leave the organization and seek work elsewhere or sink into despair at home. The loss to the community resulting from stress - related conditions is estimated to substantial.

CAUSES OF STRESS

Occupational or job stress occurs when some element of work has a negative impact on an employee's physical and mental well-being. For example, work overload and unrealistic time deadlines will put an employee under pressure and stress May occurs. Job stress cannot be separated from personal life for example, illness in the family or divorce put an employee under pressure and leads to stress. Factor that causes, stresses are numerous and their relationships complex. Incidentally, just as the factors that cause stress are numerous, in the same vein there are numerous authors who have suggested what could be the causes of stress. We shall look at the perspective of a few authors.

Bratton and Gold (1999:255) identified two major type of stressors:

Work-related factor and Individual factors

Work-related factors

A variety of work-related factors can lead to stress including role ambiguity, frustration, conflict, job design harassment, can lead to stress.

1. **Role Ambiguity:** Role ambiguity exists when the job is poorly defined; uncertainty surround job expectations and where supervisory staff and their subordinates have different expectations of an employee's responsibilities. Individuals experiencing role ambiguity may be uncertain how their performance will be evaluated and they may result to stress.

2. **Frustration:** frustration, which may result motivation being blocked to prevent an Individual from achieving a desired goal, is a major stressor. A clerical employee, trying to finish a major report before deadline, is likely to become frustrated by repeated computer breakdowns that prevent attainment of the goal.

3. Conflict: Conflicts, both interpersonal and inter-team are another source of occupational stress. When employees with different social experience, personalities, needs and points of view interact with co-workers, disagreements may cause stress.

4. Job design: Job design is another cause of stress in the workplace. Job that have limited variety of tasks, low discretion, and not active employee's upper level needs may cause stress. Huczynkis and Buchanam (1991:221) in Bratton and Gold (1999:233) report research showed that the most stressful job are those that combine high workload and low discretion.

5. Sexual Harassment: Sexual harassment at work is another source of stress. Sexual harassment can take two forms. First is a hostile environment that involves behaviour that is unwelcome and undesirable or offensive. This kind of sexual harassment would include, for example, unwanted propositions and sexual innuendo. It can be difficult for a Human Resource (HR) manager to convince employees and other managers to take this kind of sexual harassment seriously. It is often viewed as a joke, something to do with 'chatting - up' attractive female coworkers or bottom pinching. The second form sexual harassment is quid proquo harassment, which is essentially a kind of sex-for-promotion blackmail. The alleged perpetrator is normally a superior, and the blackmail is either 'given in to my sexual desire and I'll give you promotions' or 'give in or your job prospects will suffer'. Both form of harassment are aimed at women by men who occupy positions of power. Sexual harassment is stressful; it is also unlawful.

6. Individual Factors

Individual factors causing stress are equally varied and complex. Individual factor that can produce stress include financial worries, marital problems, pregnancy, problems with children, death of spouse, and dual roles.

STRESS	
Work-Related factors	Individual factors
Work overload	financial worries
Time pressures	marital problems
Lack of communication	Problems with children
Change of work	Death of spouse
Dual roles	Role ambiguity
Frustration	
Conflict at work	
Job design	

Harassment

Source: Bratton Gold J. **Human Resources Managements: Theory and Practice.** London: Macmillan Press Ltd, p.231

Providing his own perspective to the cause of stress, Tuttle 2004 maintained that the potential sources of stress are endless and everywhere. Anything that might rob us our peace and joy, and eventually compromise our health, he argued, might be considered a source of stress. Tuttle (2004) broke down the sources of stress into **major life stressors** and **daily life stressors**. The top causes for stress were identified for each category, as show blow:

Major life stressors (chronic)	Daily life stressor (acute)
Divorce	Traffic jams
Death of family member Prolonged illness Poverty Unhappiness in the workplace	Paying bills Family tension Noise Crowds Sleep disturbance Hunger
	Danger

Source: Tuttle D. (2004), “Cortisol: Keeping a Dangerous Hormones In check” **Journal of life Extension**, p.221.

Colbert (2005) provides of stress - Causing agents. His perspective has deep medical explanations. According, Colbert (2005) places stress into four general categories: **physical stress, emotional and mental stress, chemical stress, and thermal stress.** Let’s take a brief look at each one.

Physical Stress

Physical stress often arises from a lack of sleep, overworking, excessive exercise, physical injury or trauma such as a motor vehicle accident, surgery, infections, physical disease, and Chronic pain. Chronic infections are especially stressful to the body. The more severe the infections - especially pneumonia or kidney infections - and longer the infection lasts, the more the body experiences.

Emotional and Mental Stress

This area of stress is also called psychological stress. Colbert used the terms emotional, mental and psychological stress interchangeably since there’s a great deal of overlap in the medical research when it comes to these terms. Various overlap such as anger, hostility, depression, anxiety, and fear can cause chronic emotional stress. The same for “mental stress” - the worries and general anxiety that often arise from too much work and too little pay, too much debt, marital difficulties, children using drugs or alcohol, and other mental stresses related to one’s work, finances, family issues, or school. Mental stress often arises from a feeling of being overwhelmed, losing control, or feeling trapped with no way out. Perfectionists who continually strive to do more and more, and who constantly drive themselves with no real feelings of satisfaction at their own performance, are especially prone to mental stress.

A person’s brain interprets whether a situation or interaction is stressful or not. In other words, any condition or circumstance can become stressful if you think it is. One person’s stress may be another person’s pleasure.

Many people who suffer from depression, anxiety, frustration, anger, fear, and guilt have habitual distortional thought patterns that lock them into a stress - producing mentality.

Family fights pressing deadlines. Too many commitments and a too - busy lifestyle can all result in mental and emotional stress.

Chemical Stress

Chemical stress comes from excessive use of various substance such as excessive sugar, caffeine, stimulants, alcohol nicotine (cigarette smoking), and food additive's. Chemical stress is also related to substance to which a person may be exposed in the environment: mold, dust, allergies, and toxic chemicals such as diesel exhaust, second hand cigarette smoke, and pesticides. Various unwanted chemicals in our food and beverages can cause a chemical burden to the body; such as mercury in dental amalgams can cause chemical stress in fish, cadmium in shellfish, and chemical such as chlorine in tap water. Mercury in dental amalgams causes chemical stress. Marijuana is a major chemical stressor to the adrenal glands possibly owing to marijuana's effects on blood glucose levels.

Certain environments, such as crowded cities, gridlock traffic patterns, and areas with numerous factories, seem to be loaded with more chemical - related related sources than others. Not every person responds to these environmental factors in the same way, however. One person's might develop allergies asthma, recurrent infections, severe breathing problems, and adrenal fatigue in a polluted environment; another person might have no obvious physical reactions.

Thermal Stress

The final category of stress according to Colbert (2005:221) is related to being exposed to extremes in temperatures, either hot cold, for prolonged periods of time. Individuals who suffer from heart exhaustion, heart stroke, an hypothermia experience severe thermal stress. Occasionally an athlete will suffer from thermal stress by exercising to much in extreme heat. One may suffer from hypothermia after getting lost and having inadequate shelter or clothing in extremely cold condition.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The transactional theory of stress shows that people face the challenge of their capacity to adapt to inner and other demands, which may be physiologically arousing and emotionally taxing. Stress of course, is a transaction between people and their environments.

2.3 Stress in the Nigeria Tertiary Institutions

Stress has become a popular concept for explaining a wide range of behaviours that appear to defy explanation indeed it has become fashionable in the Nigeria society to attribute erratic or unexplainable behaviour of people to the fact that they are under stress.

Stress is a process in which environmental events or forces threaten the well being of an individual in the society. Stress is a disruption of the emotional stability of the individual that induces a state of disorganization in personality and behaviour (Nweze, 1984). It is a biological phenomenon that is experienced by all persons regardless of their socioeconomic status, occupation or age (Wiley, 2000). Egor (2000) viewed stress as the way the individual responds to conditions that scare, threaten, anger, bewilder or excite them. McGrth (1976)

Defines stress generally as a dynamic condition in which an individual is confronted with an opportunity, constraints, or demand on being, haring and doing what he or she desires.

Evidently, in Nigeria there are life threatening, harmful and challenging situations, which are stressful to people's existence and well-being. Some or these include economic instability, driving on poorly maintained roads, religious intolerance and insecurity. The professional and personal concerns that seem to produce stress among university teachers in Nigeria include poor salaries, the status of the profession and the feeling of inadequacy as a lecturer.

Contemporary Nigerian universities have not been immune from emerging forces of stress in the country. Despite the nation's declaration of the importance of university education in national development and the role it plays in satisfying manpower needs, there is growing evidence that there are really no universities private, states or federal that will genuinely claim to enjoy the basic facilities for teaching, learning and research. Today virtually all necessary facilities and resources, except students are in acute short supply (Nwahiani and Ofoegbu, 2001). These could expose lecturers to such levels of stress that could force them to deviate from normal functioning. Stress inducing factors in universities include lack of instructional resources, poor interpersonal relationship among staff (academic and non-academic) and between students and the administration, waves of student campus militancy and unmanageable student population. For example, during the 1995/1996, 2000/2001 and 2002/2003 academic sessions the student population of the University of Benin was 16,281, 20,364 and 24,914 respectively (University of Benin, 2003). An important related factor is government intervention in university governance. Efforts by the academicians to make the universities more responsive to the industrial and economic need of the country have been viewed as a major attack on the political elites and on intellectuals who "play politics" with the educational policies of the country; policies which according to Nwawgu (2000) should be guarded by academic considerations. Consequently some lecturers in stress inducing factors while meeting the daily learning and behavioural needs of students.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this study, the population or "unit of analysis" is the aggregate of all the teaching staff of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Since the researcher can identify all the "units of analysis" (that is all the teaching staff) with exactitude, the population of the study is defined as finite. There is total of population of one thousand, two hundred and fifty (1,250) teaching staff in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

Since the population of this study is finite and all cannot be used by the researcher, and appropriate sample size determination formula for a finite population characteristic was used. As a result the Yaro Yamane's formula for sample determination for finite population characteristics is here under adoption for this study (Okeke, 2005). the formula is stated thus: $n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$ Where:

$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$ Where:

n = Sample size
N = Population figure
E = error margin or 0.05%

Considering the population of one thousand, two hundred and fifty (1,250) teaching staff in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, the sample size was determined thus:

$$\begin{aligned} N &= 1250 \\ \frac{1 + 1250(0.05)^2}{1 + 1250(0.0025)^2} &= 1250 \\ \frac{1 + 3.125}{4.1250} &= 1250 \\ n &= 303.030 \end{aligned}$$

303

So, the sample size is three hundred and three (303) teaching staff and this was used for the study.

3.1 INSTRUMENTS FOR DATA COLLECTION

the major instruments used for data collection in this study were both primary and secondary data. Primary is "a data structure of variable that have been specifically collected and assembled for a current research problem or

opportunity situation. They represent firsthand structures (Hair et al, 2005). The primary data for this study was generated from primary sources, which include mainly responses on the questionnaire as well as responses from personal (oral or face-to-face) interview of the respondents. In designing the questionnaire, the question-response format included closed ended questions, multiple choice questions (using the modified Likert scale), dichotomous questions and checklist questions.

The secondary data, which are historical data structures of variables that were previously collected and assembled for some research problems or opportunity situation (Hair et al, 2005) was used. Three data structures were secured from secondary sources which include books, journals, newspapers, magazines and internet, etc.

3.2 DATA ANALYSIS TECHNIQUES

The statistical techniques or tools employed for analyzing or processing the data collected for this study includes frequency tables, simple percentage, mean, standard deviation, ranking and kruskal - Wallis non - parametric test. The computational formulae for the mean different tools are presented below:

Mean: $\bar{X} = \frac{\sum EX_i}{n}$

where X_i the score of a respondents, and

n is the number of respondents.

Percentage = $\frac{C_i}{N} \times 100$

C_i = Score of a subgroup

N = Total score

Standara Deviation

$SD = \sqrt{\frac{\sum EX^2}{n} - \frac{(\sum EX)^2}{n^2}}$

The Kruskal - Wallis one -way Analysis variance by Ranks

$H = \frac{12}{n(n+1)} \sum n_i R_i^2 - 3(n+1)$

Where R_i = is the sum of ranks assigned to observations in the i th group.

$N = \sum n_i$ = number of observations in all the k . groups

H is Chi-square distributed with $K - 1$ degrees of freedom

4.0 DATE PRESENTATION AND DISCUSSIONS

Biodata Or Respondent Distribution

Table 4.1 Distribution of respondents by rank and material status

Status	Professor	Reader	Snr Lect	Lect. I	Lect.II	Asst. Lect	Total

Married	12%	9%	59%	67%	81%	22%	250
Single	0%	2%	4%	5%	11%	13%	35
Divorced	2%	0%	3%	2%	0%	0%	7
Widowed	1%	1%	2%	1%	0%	0%	5
	15%	12	68	75	92	35	297

Source: Field Survey 2022

From table 4.1, it is observed that majority of the respondents are married , about 250 out of 297 (84.73%), while only 35 (11.78%) are single, 7 are divorced and 5 (1.7%) are widowed. Most of the respondents belong to the category of lecturer II, followed by lecturer I And then senior lecturer.

The number ranges from 92 (30.98%), 75 (25.25%) to 68 (22.86%)

Respectively. 35 (11.78%) of our respondents are Assistant Lecturers with just 15 (5.05%) Professors and 12 (4.04%) Reader or Associate Professors.

Table 4.2 Distribution of Respondents by Number of Children and Marital Status.

S/N	No. Of Children	Married	Single	Divorced	Widowed	Total
1	0	33	35	1	0	58
2	1 - 3	206	0	5	4	215
3	> 3	22	0	1	1	24
	Total	250	35	7	5	297

Source: Field Survey 2022

A look at table 4.2 shows that majority of the respondents, 215 (72.39%) have children ranging from 1 to 3. About 58 (19.53%) of them have no children while 24 (8.09%) have more than 3 children. Among the 250 married respondents, 206 (82.4%) of them have between 1 and 3 children while 22 (8.8%) have more than 3 Children. The same number 22 (8.8%) have no children. All the single respondents have no children, while only 1 (14.28%) of the divorced group have no child. 5(71.43%) have between 1 and 3 children while another 1 (14.28%) has more than 3 children. In the widow group, 4 (80%) have between 1 and 3 children, while 1 (20%) have more than 3 children.

4.3 DEMOGRAPHIC DATA PRESENTATION

Table 4.3 Mean Opinion of Respondents to question 1-6 of the questionnaire.

S/N	Statements	Prof	Ass. Prof	Snr Lect	Lect I	Lect II	Ass. Lect
1.	Individual do experience stress on the job.	2.9333	3.500	3.1620	3.026	3.0435	2.9714
2.	Individual do experience pressure mainly on the job. Home stress usually affects official performance .	2.8667	3.3333	3.0441	3.01000	3.0652	2.8875
3.	How do you experience stress on your job?	2.9333	3.3333	3.1471	2.96	3.2174	2.6286
4.		2.6667	3.1667	2.0609	2.5600	2.5217	2.5429
5.		3.0667	3.8333	2.6912	3.1467	2.6757	2.9714
6.		2.6667	3.3333	3.0147	2.7552	3.1333	3.04

	How would you describe your workload as a lecturer? What is the degree of stress you experience as a result of workload?						
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Source: Field Survey Results, 2022

Table 4.3 above shows the general mean to question One. Respondents generally agreed that “individuals do experience stress both on the job and at home” with a mean value of 3.071. They also conformed in question two that individuals do experience stress mainly from their job with a mean value of 3.0337. On this issue of home stress affecting official performance, a mean value of 3.0572 was obtained. When their opinion was broken down by rank, it was observed that Professor and Assistant lecturers do not so much agree to the above opinion.

S/N	Statements	No	S.D.	Mean	Remark
8d	Work load	297	2.4100	6.9125	Accepted
8a	Poor Salary	297	2.4019	6.7879	Accepted
8h	Dual roles	297	2.4533	6.7508	Accepted
8f	Unhappiness in the office	297	2.47140	6.6633	Accepted
8c	Time pressure	297	2.4619	6.5859	Accepted
8e	Poor relationship with superiors	297	2.4352	6.5522	Accepted
8g	Health conditions	297	2.8329	6.1785	Accepted
8b	Marital Status	297	2.9102	5.8990	Accepted
8e	Problem with children	297			
8j	Lack of communication	297			

When asked on how often they do experience stress, it was a general agreement that they experience stress very often, with a mean value of 2.5286. It is only the senior lecturers that actually aid they rarely experience stress. On the issue of workload, they are all of the opinion that they are over-loaded. That is their assertion on questionnaire item 6 was on the level or degree of stress that they experience at work. It was their opinion that the degree of stress was generally high (with a mean value of 3.0303) among the teaching staff.

Research Question One.

Table 4.4 Mean Opinion of Respondents on the Causes of Stress among Teaching Staff.

Source: Field work, 2022

What are the causes of stress among the teaching staff of Uninzk, Awka? To objectively answer this research question, the mean responses of the respondents on the various causes of stress were ranked. Questionnaire item number eight (8) was used and the result presented below.

Table 4.4 above shows the mean opinion of respondents on the causes of stress among teaching staff. It was observed that all the causes of stress as listed in questionnaire item 8 were all accepted, though by mean ranking in the order of magnitude, in a descending order.

Thus, the teaching staff experience stress mainly because of work they are also of the opinion that dual roles causes stress to them as well as unhappiness in the office, which might be due to one problem or the other. Time pressure and poor relationship with superiors are also some causes of stress to the teaching staff.

Research Question Two.

What are the effects of stress on the teaching staff of Nnamdi Azikiwe University. This research question was answered using responses from questionnaire item 7.

The mean opinion are ranked in a descending order

Table 4.5 Mean Opinion on the Effects of Stress on the Teaching Staff of Unizik.

S/N	Statement	NO.	S.D	Mean	Remark
7a	Decreased productivity	297	2.08353	7.3434	Accepted
7i	Frequent forgetfulness of focus	297	2.34937	7.0640	Accepted
7b	Headache, backache/chest pain	297	1.94314	6.8788	Accepted
7e	Sleep problem	297	2.30334	6.8754	Accepted
7f	Anger, Sadness/Depression	297	2.25445	6.7710	Accepted
7g	Anxiety/Restlessness	297	2.3824	6.7475	Accepted
7h	Relationship Conflict	297	2.3913	6.7273	Accepted
7d	Under/Over eating	297	2.3242	6.6768	Accepted
7c	Social withdrawal	297	2.5662	6.6532	Accepted
7j	High blood pressure/decreased immunity.	297	2.6178	6.3872	Accepted

Source: Field Survey, 2022.

The major effect of stress is “decreased work productivity”. This is followed by headache, back pain, chest pain. Others are social withdrawal, under eating/over eating, sleeping problem, anger, sadness/depression, anxiety/restlessness; relationship conflict frequent forgetfulness/lack of focus; high blood pressure, and or decreased immunity.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING HYPOTHESIS ONE:

There is no significant difference in the causes of stress among the various ranks of the teaching staff in Unizik. To objectively test hypothesis One, the respondent’s responses to question 3 of section A and that of question 8 of section B are combined.

The responses to question 8 are ranked and since they are non-parametric in nature, KruskalWallis test is used. Table 4.7 below shows the result to the various options of the question items.

Table 4.7 Kruskal - Wallis Test Result for Hypothesis One.

S/N	Rank of Respondents	Mean Rank	Chi-square Value	Probability Value (0.05)	Remark
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Quest 8a	Professor	176.1	3.00		
	Associate Prof.	161.75			
	Senior Lecturer	139.95			
	Lecturer I	145.25			
	Lecturer	149.82			
	Assistant Lecturer	156.47			
	II		0.70	Accepted	
8b	Professor	150.73	6.13	0.294	Accepted
	Associate Prof.	120.83			
	Senior Lecturer	157.03			
	Lecturer I	146.46			
	Lecturer II	156.11			
	Assistant Lecturer	123			
8c	Professor	169.07			
	Associate Prof.	162.50			
	Senior Lecturer	136.81	4.546	0.474	Accepted
	Lecturer I	140.62			
	Lecturer II	158.92			
	Assistant Lecturer	151.33			
8d	Professor	128.23	4.482	0.482	Accepted
	Associate Prof.	161.13			
	Senior Lecturer	135.51			
	Lecturer I	157.00			
	Lecturer II	148.97			
	Assistant Lecturer	162.90			

8e	Professor Associate Prof. Senior Lecturer Lecturer I Lecturer II Assistant Lecturer	162.50 191.71 146.10 162.98 144.64 115.69	11.076	0.05	Rejected
8f	Professor Associate Prof. Senior Lecturer Lecturer I Lecturer II Assistant Lecturer	149.43 110.00 152.42 153.17 160.95 115.20	10.159	0.071	Accepted
8h	Professor Associate Prof. Senior Lecturer Lecturer I Lecturer II Assistant Lecturer	139.3 116.67 144.18 139.49 160.27 164.37	5.875	0.319	Accepted
8i	Professor Associate Prof. Senior Lecturer Lecturer I Lecturer II Assistant Lecturer	144.57 190.17 154.88 161.34 148.16 101.13	15.908	0.007	Rejected
8j	Professor Associate Prof. Senior Lecturer Lecturer I Lecturer II Assistant Lecturer	201.4 215.85 136.99 159.99 130.79 151.27	19.814	0.001	Rejected

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From the table 4.7, the null hypothesis was rejected in three cases while it shows that there is significant differences in the causes of stress among the various ranks of the teaching staff in Unizik.

(a) All the staff, whether academics or non academics do experience stress both from job and at home, but mostly from their jobs. However, home stressors generally affects the official performance of many academic staff. The teaching staff also experience stress due to work overload and dual roles resulting from lack of academic lecturers. Others include time pressure and lack of cordial relationship with superiors.

(b) The major effects of stress include decrease in productivity, social withdrawal and depression. Others are anxiety, relationship conflicts, lack of focus, high blood pressure and decreased immunity. Of course, Colbert (2001) comments that mental depression often arises from a feeling of being overwhelmed, losing control or feeling trapped. According to him, perfectionists who continually drive themselves with no feeling of satisfaction at their own performance are generally prone to mental depression

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that stressors abound in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awaka and affects both teaching and non-teaching staff alike. That these stressors retard teachers' productivity and impede the academic performance of students, as they are not adequately attended to. Owing to the above, there is therefore, the need to determine the optimal level of stress, which can individually motivate and not overwhelm the teaching staff of the university. And as the incidence of stressors increase among the teaching staff, there should be different management strategies for coping with it.

In the light of the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Teachers should not be overload with courses. Since it is obvious that the University established different programmes ranging Regular, continuing Education (CEP), Sandwich, Pre-science, to Post-Graduate (PG), there should be stipulated maximum academic load per lecturer in any of the these programmes
2. Appropriate communication system should be established in the university system. The university management should create an interactive forum where the lecturers should be made to know what is happening in their environment, so as to equip themselves for the future challenges. An uninformed individual is a deformed individual. So, information should be made to flow among the different strata of the university system.
3. Priority should be accorded to the health care programme of the university. Health they say is wealth. Adequate healthcare system in terms of availability and affordability in area as of maternal and childcare HIV/AIDS, childcare diseases, hypertension, diabetes, etc, would ensure teachers' confidence and engender productivity. Stress, particularly, mental depression results mainly out of situational uncertainties and which should not be allowed to happen at all.

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